

CULTURAL TOURISM AS A POSSIBLE DRIVER OF RURAL DEVELOPMENT IN CZECHIA. WINE TOURISM IN MORAVIA AS A CASE STUDY

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Abstract: The paper connects culture, tourism and rural development. It tries to make an overview of various forms of cultural tourism in Czechia. Attractions of cultural tourism are identified and ranked according to their cognitive function. Their list includes cultural heritage in spheres of archaeological sites, architecture, arts, folklore, pilgrimages, technical works, cultural events or protected landscape areas. The culture of wine in Southern Moravia has been chosen as an example. Its analysis was elaborated using the Importance/Performance Analysis. Czechia has great potential for the cultural tourism development in rural areas but it seems to demand a great deal of work when one needs to be constantly reconciling the changing interests of tourists with the potential of the regions. One of the important goals is to attract tourists into rural areas and thus limit their concentration in the most attractive places. Rural cultural tourism seems to be a significant aspect in this respect. The part of the study is the example of the adaptation of the current situation with COVID-19 to properly support the development and cultural potential of domestic tourism in South Moravian region in relation to the economic impacts on international tourism.

Key words: cultural tourism, culture of wine, rural development, Czechia, COVID-19

Souhrn: Příspěvek spojuje kulturu, cestovní ruch a rozvoj venkova. Snaží se podat přehled o různých formách kulturního cestovního ruchu v Česku. Atraktivita kulturního cestovního ruchu jsou identifikovány a uspořádány podle jejich kognitivní funkce. Jejich -seznam zahrnuje kulturní dědictví v oblastech archeologických nalezišť, architektury, umění, folklóru, pout, technických děl, kulturních akcí nebo chráněných krajinných oblastí. Jako příklad byla vybrána kultura vína na jižní Moravě. Její analýza byla zpracována pomocí analýzy důležitosti / výkonu. Česko má velký potenciál pro rozvoj kulturního cestovního ruchu ve venkovských oblastech, ale jeho využití vyžaduje velkou práci neustálého sladování měnících se zájmů turistů s potenciálem regionů. Jedním z důležitých cílů je rozptýlení turistů do venkovského prostoru a tím omezení jejich koncentrace v nejatraktivnějších místech. V tomto směru hraje venkovský kulturní cestovní ruch významnou roli. Součástí studie je aktuální využití kulturního potenciálu regionu jižní Morava pro podporu rozvoje domácího cestovního ruchu v souvislosti s dopady pandemie COVID-19 na mezinárodní cestovní ruch.

Klíčová slova: kulturní cestovní ruch, kultura vína, rozvoj venkova, Česko, COVID-19

1. Introduction

Following cities, the countryside is also undergoing a transition from an industrial to a post-industrial stage of development. Although the agriculture and forestry are still decisive for the maintenance of rural landscape, the countryside is no longer exclusively a space for the primary production but more and more an area for the consumption of its physical and spiritual values. Similarly, numbers and shares of people engaged in the primary and later also in the secondary sectors, substantially decrease. Villages are no more settlements of farmers but more and more locale of people commuting for work to towns and cities or engaged in various branches of services.

Thus, a question is raised: which activities could substitute the agriculture and forestry to keep rural landscape and settlement. Experts in different levels respond to this question setting tourism as their first priority. However, from such a response other questions arise: what sort of tourism categories should be taken into account, under what conditions are they able to substitute productive branches.

Tourism in the production era is aimed mostly on a regeneration of working force. Present post-industrial tourism prefers the consumption of attractions. Through tourism, the rural landscapes and the countryside are commodified, which may lead to replacing rural values for the price which

the consumers are willing to pay (Woods, 2011). Post productive tourism is represented by a tourism movement from the traditional mass tourism 'sun and beach' resorts to diversified tourism commodities (Gómez y Patiño, Xavier Medina and Puyelo Arilla, 2016).

Czech elderly (or do you mean Czech Seniors +65yrs) for 15 years annually take 31.6 million trips², where 26 million trips were within Czechia. They spend 96 million nights on accommodation there, which means almost 11 overnights per inhabitant. In the same time, 31.1 million foreigners visit Czechia, 12.2 million of them spend at least one night there. They come from Germany (16%), Italy, United Kingdom, Slovakia, France, the USA, Spain etc. Foreign tourists spend about 9 million EUR in Czechia annually. Of it, 90% of expenses are spent for transport and accommodation before the trip and 36% for goods, 26% for accommodation, 22% for board, 6% for transport and 3% for fuels during the trip. The problem is that 74% of foreign tourists head to Prague. The South Moravian Region is on the second place with 8.6% but the majority (5 percentage points) is accommodated in Brno. It means that the countryside is rarely visited till this present time.

The paper is aimed at the identification of the importance of cultural tourism in the Czech tourism industry and its possible role for the rural development. An analysis of the wine tourism in Moravia serves as a case study.

2. Cultural tourism

Richards (1996) connects culture and tourism. He argues that the relation is not coincidental. Widening of both tourism and culture is one of the results of basic societal transformation of the second half of the 20th century. Cultural tourism can be defined simply as a visitation of cultural artefacts. Their list could include archaeological sites, architecture, arts, folklore, pilgrimages etc., whereas each of the items could be broadly expanded. An involvement of tourist into cultural processes is another aspect.

Mousavi et al. (2016) distinguish between the conceptual and the technical definitions. The first one states: "*Cultural tourism is the movement of persons to cultural activities away from their formal place of residence, with the intension to gather new information and experience to satisfy their cultural needs*". The second one professes that "*Cultural tourism is all movements of persons to specific cultural attractions, such as heritage sites, artistic and cultural manifestations, arts and drama outside their normal place of residence*". The first definition comprehensively covers the issue, based on the general definition of culture. However, it is impractical, because the research would have to examine the intentions or motivations of tourism participants in relation to the given attractiveness. The second definition, on the other hand, allows comparatively accessible statistical or similar surveys, but it does not allow the determination of tourists' motivations – that is, whether they actually visit the place in order to expand their cultural knowledge. Moreover, many tourists visit foreign regions with multi-aiming interests – to combine travels for recreation or business with cultural purposes.

McIntosh, Goeldner and Ritchie (1995) define cultural tourism as *all aspects of travel, whereby travellers learn about the history and heritage of others or about their contemporary ways of life and thought*. This definition includes the culture in its wide sense of its material and non-material aspects. It is clear that under such a wide understanding, a wide variety of individual activities could be included under the concept of cultural tourism as follows:

It is possible to mention (without any demand on a completeness) such forms of tourism like the gastronomic tourism (Gheorghe, Tudorache and Nistoreanu, 2014, Kumar Dixit, 2019) including wine (Blegoli et al., 2016), beer (Csapó and Wetzl, 2016) or even whisky routes (Stoffelen and Vanneste, 2015), religious tourism (Griffin and Raj, 2017) including pilgrimage ways (Bambi et al., 2019), battlefield and military tourism (Dunkley, Morgan and Westwood, 2011), folklore and ethnographic tourism including folklore festivals (Bochenek, 2013), visiting of the UNESCO World heritage sites (Poria, Reichel and Cohen, 2013), traditional cultural tourism exploring museums, galleries, monuments and other places of interest and also zoos and safari

² Czech Tourism Agency

tourism, visiting places of movies and TV series (Reijnders, 2016), even the industrial culture (Härfst, Pizzera and Simic (2016) and many others. At the same time, there are modes of tourism which are not originally cultural but they could include some cultural aspects like eco-cultural tourism (Wallace and Russell, 2004).

Originally, the tourism including the cultural one was accessible for the elite class. It was connected with the creation of museums, exhibitions and monuments. It presupposed relatively rich consumers with important cultural knowledge. The situation is changing after tourism has become increasingly of interest to the middle class in the post-industrial society. It is becoming a massive character and its subject of its interest is expanding. At present, cultural tourism has been identified as a major growth area in European tourism (Richards and Bonink, 1995).

Cultural tourism had a special importance for the post-communist countries of Central and Eastern Europe (Hughes and Allen, 2005). It was extremely important to get to know the regions and inhabitants on the other side of the Iron Curtain after 40 years of very limited contacts. In this regard, the cultural tourism is not only generally cultural but also a political aspect (Hall, 2017). Szörenyiné Kukorelli (2011) mentioned that tourist service providers learned their businesses in western countries. She highlighted that middle class tourists in rural space are interested in biking, hiking, horse riding, swimming, in the winter skiing or other sports. Cultural activities serve mostly like additional ones.

Our approach tries to connect the tourism and the culture with the rural development. According to Lane and Kastenzholz (2015), cultural and heritage tourism is a vast field within which rural heritage and culture play a strong role. However, the definition of rural is also complicated. It is possible to discuss whether it is understood as villages with surrounded landscape or as rural micro-regions including small towns as their natural centres. In both cases, the question of a limit between village and town and between small and medium-size town is questionable. Hall and Mitchell (2005) state that rural tourism should be located in rural areas, functionally rural, small in scale, traditional and diverse.

The connection of the culture and the rural puts a question of the cultural potential of the countryside, which could be used for the touristic purposes and its possible differences from the urban potential for cultural tourism. We are of the opinion that the rural milieu which is less globalized keeps regional and local identity more faithfully than globalized cities. According to Silva and Leal (2015), the cultural tourism even contributes to the national identity. From this viewpoint, the countryside could play a very important role in the cultural tourism. However, some authors highlight a threat of the disappearance of rural (Storey, 2004).

The connection of the tourism and the rural includes two mutually penetrated categories: rural tourism and the tourism in the countryside. Rural tourism can be understood as such tourism which uses the countryside of different quality as a leading or at least an important attractiveness. Tourism in the countryside is any tourism, which is situated in the rural space not taking into account whether it primarily uses the rural milieu as the most important attractiveness, or whether it could be situated in any place. Of course, not each way of the rural tourism can be considered as a cultural one. In some European countries, second housing is the most frequent way of the rural tourism (Roca, 2016), which is hardly a sort of cultural tourism.

Richards (2018) states a shift from tangible to intangible heritage. More attention is also paid to indigenous and other minority groups. Cultural rural tourism could be also understood as compatible with the concept of smart village (Garau, 2015).

Tourism has started to be a mass feature. In this connection, the question of its sustainability has come into account. The situation is often paradoxical: to substitute agriculture for tourism from the viewpoint of benefit and jobs, the tourism should be massive. Nevertheless, the massive tourism could cause an overloading of the landscape and by such a way, a loss of its attractiveness and consequently a downfall of tourism. Another time, a tourism aiming to explore less developed rural areas where old customs and rural lifestyle have been preserved, can bring funds to the area for which the locals improve their lives towards globalized practices and thus the reason to visit the region disappears (Šťastná, Vaishar and Pákozdiová, 2015). Also, the relation between local population and tourists (support or opposition, economic or non-

economic motivations) is very important (Strzelecka, Bynum Boley and Strzelecka, 2016). It also seems that in aged rural micro-regions, local people living from a pension or other social support, and thus not depending on local economy, are not friendly towards mass tourism development.

In the rural space, also the relation between agriculture and tourism is important. In general, trends aim at a substitution of agriculture by the tourism (e.g., Granberg, 2017). However, agriculture remains the most important activity in rural space. There is a question of a coexistence of agriculture and tourism. The agri-tourism (Barbieri et al., 2015) is one of the possibilities. On the other hand, only the intensive agriculture is competitively able without subsidies. Is it possible to combine the intensive agriculture with tourism or would it be better to separate these two sectors?

Who should be the consumer of rural cultural tourism? It is probably possible to exclude rich urban travelers who ask for first-class services and infrastructure. These people are usually separated from normal rural life. Even if they visit the countryside, they use only selected services surrounded by qualified personnel. They live in cities and make maximum optional trips to the countryside. However, getting to know foreign regions and their inhabitants means to be free not only from administrative barriers and zones of limited security but also from their own demand for high-class services and infrastructure.

Consequently, rural cultural tourism should be directed more for the middle class, young people and students, families or lovers of culture. Similarly, Eusébio et al. (2017) identify four categories of consumers of rural tourism: the active visitors, the passive observers of nature, the inactive and the summer family vacationers. The shift to intangible attractiveness means a higher demand on the preparedness of the tourists (they should have a basic knowledge of history, geography, languages). Instead of passive consumption, cultural tourists demonstrate a proactive approach to meeting their needs, wanting to actively participate in experiences while travelling. On the other hand, suppliers focus their attention on the close interaction with consumers and co-creation of high-quality experiences (Vasiliadis et al., 2016).

3. A brief evidence of the cultural rural tourism in Czechia

In Czechia, the Czech Tourism Agency (2019) publishes some statistics about visiting individual attractiveness or their groups. Prague castle with 2,445 visitors is the most visited attraction. Only the 20th most visited attraction could be considered for rural and cultural. It is Kamenice gorge in Bohemian Switzerland with 402,000 visitors. The Walachian open air museum in Rožnov pod Radhoštěm takes the 28th place with 354,000 visitors followed by the Lipno treetop walkway on the 31st place with 342,000 visitors etc. Of the group attractions, the Cave Administration of the Czech Republic reported 783,000 tourists taking the 5th place.

However, to analyse the cultural tourism by means of statistical data has some difficulties. The first problem is how to differentiate the cultural tourism from other tourist activities. Many tourists combine the cultural tourism with relaxation, sport, business, health tourism etc. A visit of the same activity could be motivated differently by various tourists. The second problem is connected with the statistics. Some tourist activities are registered very well – especially those which are paid or those which are connected with an accommodation. A use of other ones can only be estimated. Moreover, statistics hardly record a quality of culture consumption. Some problems could be connected also with a differentiation between rural from urban attractiveness.

The rural cultural tourism is not aimed at the quantity of visitors and the mass character so much. The knowledge of which tourist can gain and the identity creating individual rural regions are substantial. We try to characterize individual aspects of the cultural rural tourism in Czechia (Šťastná et al., 2015). The rural cultural tourism will be divided into the following parts: (1) nature and homeland values, (2) history, (3) architecture and urban planning, (4) folklore, ethnography and rural habits, (5), religious values, (6) gastronomy, (7) personalities and media, (8) technical works and monuments.

- (1) The Czech Republic operates (2018) 4 national parks (Giant Mts., Bohemian Forest Mts., Bohemian Switzerland, Dyje River valley), 26 protected landscape areas, 109 national natural reserves, 810 natural reserves, 124 national natural monuments and 1,556 natural

monuments (Agency of the Nature and Landscape Protection). The large protected areas take 12,565 km², which represents 16% of the Czech territory. Urban population can gain knowledge in many zoos, botanical gardens and arboretums. With some exceptions, these facilities are not possible to consider for rural, although they belong to the most visited – headed with zoo in Prague with 1,428,000 visitors, followed by zoo in Zlín (648,000 visitors), Ostrava (537,000 visitors), safari in Dvůr Králové nad Labem (525,000 visitors), etc. Treetop walkways could now be partly classified with the natural tourism, although it is usually highly commodified. Composed cultural landscape of Lednice-Valtice area is a part of the UNESCO World heritage since 1996. A different character has the montane cultural landscape of the Ore Mts., which was announced as part of the UNESCO cultural heritage in 2019. There are some cave systems, of which the Moravian karst with the Macocha abyss (217,000 visitors in 2018) is the best known. Besides this, there are many other occasions to get to know nature and landscape. Czechia is situated on the border of two main biogeographical provinces, two important mountain ranges (the Alps and the Carpathians) and 4 sub-provinces of Europe and, also at the same time in the main European watershed between Elbe, Danube and Oder basins. This predetermines the existence of many diverse and diversified landscapes on a relatively small area. The entry to Czech forests and fields is mostly free and the movement in open landscape is safe. It means that the potential of getting to know natural and open landscape attractions in Czechia is relatively high. Vantage towers cover the territory of the country, Štramberk (66,000 visitors) being the most visited rural one. On the other hand, the cultural tourism in natural landscape has its limits to keep the sustainability. Especially, national parks could be endangered by the mass tourism development.

- (2) Czechia is situated in the centre of Europe, where the interests of European powers blend – not speaking about their own Czech contribution to the European history. The battlefields are probably the most attractive historical places. The Austerlitz battlefield (120 km²) is probably the best known. The key event dedicated to the anniversary of the battle in December is annually visited by more than 10,000 visitors and 1,000 actors. However, the total annual number of visitors is much higher (the Cairn of Piece with a museum report 21,000 visitors). Of other battlefields, battle by Hradec Králové (1866) and many others offer occasions for tourists. A special type of military history is captured in the form of the military fortifications from the time of threat to Nazi Germany. The Hůrka artillery fortress in Králíky being the most visited one (30,000 visitors). The WWII is remembered with the Second World War Memorial in Hrabyně (21 thousand visitors) and especially with Terezín memorial (a concentration camp for Jewish population; 297,000 visitors) or the Lidice memorial.
- (3) Architectural monuments belong to the strengths of the Czech cultural tourism. Although their majority is situated in cities and towns, plenty such monuments can be found also in rural areas. The unique set of so-called rural baroque in the village Holašovice is a part of the UNESCO World heritage since 1998. Above that, there are 61 rural memorial reserves in Czechia. Rural buildings are preserved in open air museums. The Walachian open-air museum in Rožnov pod Radhoštěm is the most visited of them. However, it is possible to name also the Museum of Folk Architecture in Kouřim, Museum of the Highland on the Veselý kopec hill, Elbe Ethnologic Museum in Přerov nad Labem, Haná Open Air Museum in Příkazy; together 16 open air museums and 12 individual buildings. Also, rural buildings in protected landscape areas are under a protection. The problem consists in a contradiction between the owners, who are interested in adapting their property to current needs and the protectors who insists on “an original state”. On the other side, western township is not consider as a part of the cultural tourism because they serve more as entertainment. Castles and chateaus form a very interesting category. It is said that Czechia disposes with the densest network of feudal buildings in Europe, numbering about 2,700 objects. Although many of them are situated in urban milieu and a big part of these buildings are in ruins or in the form of ground remnants, there is a big number of castles and chateaus also in rural areas. Many of them – both state and private – are accessible to the public. The following are most visited: Lednice chateau (394,000 visitors 2018),

Hluboká nad Vltavou chateau (289,000), Dětenice chateau (243,000), the royal castle Karlštejn (224,000), Valtice chateau (194,000 thousand) etc. There are some other profane buildings or constructions (e.g., bridges) in rural areas.

- (4) Some rural folklore intangible activities are within the UNESCO World Heritage as well: male folk dance verbuňk (South-Eastern Moravia), rural carnival “masopust” (Bohemian-Moravian Highland), falconry (together with 10 other countries), the ride of Kings (Moravian Slovakia and Haná regions), folk puppetry (the whole territory of the country) and the blueprint (Strážnice and Olešnice in Moravia). The folklore is represented by important events, International Folklore Festival Strážnice since 1946 (32,000 visitors in 2019) being the leading activity. There are many other international, national and regional events. Some of them penetrate to cities or to the regions where the cultural tradition was interrupted after the WWII. Attempts to renew old handicrafts form usually a part of the new tradition. The tradition of folk celebrations is artificially renewing or implemented to support the tourism. Nevertheless, the living folklore survives mainly in Moravia where the folk tradition is not only commercial but it is partly a part of the life style of local population. It is closely connected with the culture of wine (in Southern Moravia) or other gastronomic tradition. The folklore is closely connected with the religion which serves as an indicator of the traditional life style rather than an indicator of the trust in the Czech conditions. Churches are often the only valuable buildings and dominants of the Czech villages. During 40 years of the communist regime, the Church was persecuted but paradoxically, the maintenance of remaining church buildings (which were not destroyed or more often used for not church proposes) was paid by the state. So, the network of rural churches and small constructions as chapels, calvaries, crosses is relatively dense, notwithstanding the mending of fields and destroying many dirt roads, connected with the collectivization. These constructions form an important part of the contemporary values of the cultural landscape (Šťastná et al., 2018).
- (5) Of the pilgrimage places, National Pilgrimage in Velehrad in Eastern Moravia, connected with the tradition of the Great Moravia Empire, St. Constantin and St. Methodius is the most important with dozens of thousands of visitors. The tradition of pilgrimage ways is slowly disappearing. There are also other pilgrimage places and ways. For instance, Holy Hostýn, Holy Mountain near Příbram, St. Wenceslaus pilgrimage Stará Boleslav, Křtiny pilgrimage, St. Antonius in Blatnice, Klokoty in Southern Bohemia, Mountain of the Mother of Lord in Králíky and many others. It seems that religious constructions become less religious and more ecumenical and a part of the cultural heritage. Religious monuments are often maintained as a part of the cultural heritage rather than church facilities. It is true especially for synagogues in small towns in the situation when there are hardly any practising Jews in these settlements.
- (6) Gastronomy forms an important part of the rural culture and an interesting motivation for visiting rural areas. In the Czech conditions, it is connected often with alcoholic beverages: the culture of wine in Southern Moravia, culture of beer mostly in Bohemia or culture of brandy in Walachia and other regions. Other local products also contribute to this branch of tourism. Some culinary festivals are organized annually like Prague Food Festival, Gastrofest in České Budějovice or Salima Brno to help to increase motivations to visit regions with typical foods. Moreover, some specialised festivals (like Asparagus festival in Ivančice) can attract visitors. A logo “Taste Moravia” serves as advertising. The original Czech cuisine is not very healthy, but can be attractive. The idea of *slow food* is penetrating slowly into the Czech gastronomy.
- (7) Places, where famous personalities were born, active or died can also attract the tourists’ interest. Museum of Tomáš Garrigue Masaryk in Lány (19,000 visitors) is the most frequently visited, followed by Josef Lada memorial in Hrusice, Karel Čapek memorial in Stará Huť, Božena Němcová museum in Česká Skalice, Mendelianum in Brno and many others. It is interesting that the visitors pay their attention also to the non-existing personalities like the good soldier Švejk, Jára Cimrman or persons from tales like robber Rumcajs in the surroundings of Jičín and others. Places and regions where novels were situated or movies or TV series were filmed are relatively new aims of tourists. Of

the traditional places, let us namely the Grandmother's valley near Ratibořice, the scene of the Božena Němcová novel *Grandmother*. The South-Bohemian village Hořtice is a popular place of the triptych *Sun, hay and ...* The crime series *Police Modrava* was very closely connected with the surroundings of Kašperské Hory town, which represents also a big potential. Existing database³ of film shots identifies more than 39,000 places within Czechia, where Czech and/or foreign films were filmed. This database serves for tourism proposes among others.

- (8) Technical heritage but also contemporary technical works represent next category of cultural heritage. The database⁴ contains more than 1,300 objects. Many of them are situated in cities and towns of course. However, some of them can be found also in rural areas. They form a relatively wide spectrum of different constructions like bridges, buildings for water management, mining constructions, energetic facilities, factories, wind and water mills, tunnels, granaries, riding stables and many others. Of the contemporary facilities, Dlouhé stráně pump power plant recorded 98,000 of visitors followed by the Dukovany nuclear power plant with 36,000 of visitors in 2018.

A relative complex overview of rural tourism in South-Moravian region was elaborated by Štátná et al. (2015). The authors mention three possible contributions of rural tourism: a substitution of a part of working force released from agriculture, economic benefit and increasing of general knowledge about the region. The last item is in fact the matter of the cultural tourism. In this connection, the authors also highlight the increasing importance of foreign tourists. Peruthová and Ryglová (2018) define three profiles of a typical visitor to a rural destination: students (18–26 years), young adults (27–35 years) and an empty nest (46–55 years). In general, natural beauties, relaxation and experiences are among the strongest motives for traveling to a rural tourist destination. These motifs fully correspond to the nature of the destination. The most frequent activities are hiking in nature, typical summer activities such as swimming or visiting historical and cultural monuments. A typical rural tourist uses a car to travel to a destination and uses the guesthouse accommodation. The visitor usually spends 2–3 days in a rural destination. These results correspond to the results presented above, when the dependence of most of the studied quality factors of the destination in terms of importance and satisfaction on the age of the visitor was proved.

4. Tourism and culture of wine in Southern Moravia as a case study

The following case study refers to issues of wine destinations in South Moravia with regard to destination quality and visitor's satisfaction in the wine areas.

The 96% of Czech wineries are located in Southern Moravia (southeast part of Czechia). Wine production before the 1990s, the transformation of socialistic political system into democracy so-called Velvet revolution, was oriented strongly on quantity. After the 1990s, the whole wine sector began to move towards quality, which was connected with related branches like wine tourism. Nowadays, the South Moravia region is considered as traditional wine-growing region where wine production and the associated culture, next to the cultural, historical and natural attractions, are one of the main reasons for visiting this area (Prokeš, 2019).

In terms of location, Czechia can be divided into the two wine regions of Bohemia and Moravia (see Figure 1). There are two sub-regions in Bohemia (Mělník and Litoměřice), and about 72 wine-growing villages, 152 vineyards, 160 growers, total area of vineyards being 643 hectares. Moravia, on the other hand, comprise 4 sub-regions (Znojmo, Mikulov, Velké Pavlovice and Moravian Slovakia), 312 wine-growing villages, 1,126 vineyards, 18,511 growers and the total area of vineyards is 17,098 hectares⁵. The vegetative season is shorter than in Western Europe and the annual average temperature reaches 9.42 °C. The most widespread grape varieties are

³ <https://www.filmovamista.cz/zaber/hledanamista>

⁴ <http://www.technickepamatky.cz/>

⁵ Historie a fakta [online]. [cit. 2020-01-15]. Accessible from: <https://www.wineofczechrepublic.cz/nase-vina/historie-a-fakta/statistiky-a-fakta.html>; <https://www.cmb-brno2020.cz/cs/vinarstvi-v-cr/vinarske-regiony/>

Grüner Veltliner and Müller Thurgau among the white ones and Blaufränkisch and Saint Laurent represent blue varieties⁶. Statistics (CSU, 2018) show that the average amount of wine consumed in the Czechia per person per year is about 20 litres⁷. The popularity of wine tourism is rising every year among the Czech people.

Fig 1. Wine regions and sub-regions in Czechia. Source: National Wine Center⁸

Wine tourism is a type of rural tourism, which activities take place in rural areas/countryside and which is connected with business activities of wine producers, usually taking place in wine regions, wine cellars (Fig. 3), wineries.

Lane (1994) pointed out that it is not easy to find a unified definition that could be applied to all countryside areas in all countries world-wide. Wine tourism could be explained as a category of agrotourism, which is according to Zelenka and Pásková (2012) provided by farmers and agrobusiness as a complementary activity to their main production agricultural activities. Vystoupil and Šauer (2006) distinguish five types of wine tourism (see Fig. 2):

The cultural-cognitive form of the wine tourism is connected with getting to know folklore customs, traditions, folklore, architecture and life in the wine villages in the past and present. Recreational-wine tourism is related to the restoration of strength and relaxation. It can be associated with relaxation in the nature, by the water, staying in the spa or other popular wellness activities.

The rapid development of wine bicycle tourism is due to the construction of an extensive chain of wine cycle paths linking wine villages. In South Moravia, there are the Moravian Wine Trails. These trails were created with the cooperation of the Nadace Partnerství Foundation and with 250 wine villages and with the support of the State Fund for Rural Renewal. There are 18 trails in total: Brno WT, Bzenec WT, Region André, Kyjov WT, Mikulov WT, Modré hory, Moravian WT – Mikulov, Moravian WT – Slovácká, Moravian WT – Velké Pavlovice, Moravian WT – Znojmo, Mutěnice WT, Skalická, Stará hora, Strážnice WT, Uherské Hradiště WT, Velké Pavlovice WT, Podluží WT and Znojmo WT. The total area of biking trails in Czechia is about 3,500 km, where the Moravian Wine Trails cover 1,200 km.

⁶ National Wine Center, <https://www.cmb-brno2020.cz/en/viticulture-in-cr/wine-regions/>

⁷ Historie a fakta [online]. [cit. 2020-01-15]. Dostupné z: <https://www.wineofczechrepublic.cz/nase-vina/historie-a-fakta/statistiky-a-fakta.html>

⁸ <https://www.cmb-brno2020.cz/en/viticulture-in-cr/wine-regions/>

Fig. 2 Wine tourism typology. Source: Vystoupil and Šauer (2006)

Moreover, the form of socially oriented wine tourism is experiencing a rapid development today. Social events connected with the wine culture can be attended almost all year round. Prokeš (2019) defines the following as the main events in South Moravia:

- Festival, celebration (e.g. folklore festivals, wine festivals, feasts, grape harvest, St. Martin's festivals)
- Tasting, competition
- Fair markets
- Courses, seminars
- Food festivals
- Adventure tours
- Other events connected with sports and wine, art and wine, etc.

The most known events are the International Folklore Festival in Strážnice, the Znojmo Wine Festival, the Open Cellars Festival, the Vineyards by Bike, the TOP Wine of Slovácko, the Open Cellars in Pavlov, the Cellar to the Cellar and many others.

An economically oriented form of wine tourism is associated with professional seminars, oenology courses, wine competitions and nowadays popular sommelier and tasting workshops.

Fig 3. Wine cellars in Vrbice (Hodonín district). Source: V. Stodolová

The fact that the majority of the Czech vineyard areas (96%) is allocated to the South Moravian region predestines this region as a place with a high potential for the development of wine tourism. At the same time, it is important to mention that the wine tourism market is very competitive due to the wide variety of offerings of wine tourism services and products not only in Czechia but also in nearby regions of Austria, Hungary or Slovakia. Competitiveness according to Hassan (2000) refers to a destination's ability to create and integrate value-added products that sustain its resources while maintaining market position relative to competitors and the relative ability of a destination to meet visitor needs on various aspects of the tourism experience, or to deliver goods and services that perform better than other destinations on those aspects of the tourism experience considered to be important by tourists (Dwyer, Kim; 2003).

Pásková (2009) describes wine destination as one rich in folk architecture, local traditions, customs, products, and cultural landscape. Wine is an essential product of wine tourism but its quality is not only one factor. According to wine tourism, quality can be measured. In wine tourism destination you can meet a number of "players" who enter mutual interactions: winemakers, providers of wine cellars, wine shops, wine restaurants, wine bars, accommodation with wine theme, wine wellness, wine trails; organizers of wine events, wine exhibitions and other service providers like tourist or nature attractions providers and other entrepreneurs; municipalities and – last but not least – local people. All these stakeholders create a huge package/network of services that can influence overall wine tourist satisfaction and wine customer loyalty.

The following section reveals the research results which seeks to identify the *wine destination quality factors* importance and to their performance at the destination through customer satisfaction.

Methodology

The research destination quality factors used in the survey were chosen on basis of authors previous empirical research (Ryglová et al., 2017; 2018) adopted with wine destination type. The primary data have been obtained by online questionnaire among Czech respondents and at the same time visitors of wine destination, where the questions regarding the satisfaction and importance of quality factors were formulated using five-point Likert scale (number five represents the highest significance/satisfaction of/with an individual factor). The satisfaction with quality factors was measured among 271 respondents (50% women and 50% men) and the importance

of quality factors was measured by 400 respondents (60% women and 40% men. Kruskal-Wallis test was used to find out which quality factors are depending on gender and age of visitors. Importance-Performance Analysis (IPA) was used to evaluate factors in the context of destination management (Rasovska et al., 2020). The result of IPA framework is the plot, which classifies quality factors into four categories in order to set priorities in allocating the resources. Typically, the four quadrants are: Keep up the good work, Possible overkill, Low priority and Concentrate here. The threshold within the IPA plot was computed as the median of mean values of the importance and performance of the quality factors (Sever, 2015).

Results

The table 1 depicts the destination quality factors due to their importance for visitors of wine destination. As the most significant factor, not surprisingly, the quality of wine (F21) was found. The next 7 factors reached average evaluation above value 4 on 5th point scale. These quality factors (F13: F15: F14: F12: F10: F4: F20) are also very significant to the wine destination visitor.

Tab 1. The order of quality factors based on the significance perceived by the visitors of wine destination. Source: authors research (scale of significance 1–5, where 5 – represented a very high importance of the factor)

		Mean	Median	Std. Dev.
21	Quality of wine	4.557	5	0.765
13	Level of personnel quality in tourism services	4.434	5	0.783
15	Destination cleanliness	4.423	5	0.781
14	Sense of security	4.258	4	0.910
12	Level of prices of services and goods in the destination	4.223	4	0.830
10	Friendly acceptance by the locals	4.198	4	0.914
4	Food	4.158	4	0.871
20	Quality of wine commentary	4.108	4	0.936
5	Social and experiential events	3.993	4	1.007
3	Accommodation	3.973	4	0.910
8	Availability and quality of information in the destination	3.898	4	0.885
16	Overcrowding of the destination	3.876	4	0.987
9	Information and communication prior to arrival	3.840	4	0.940
24	Price advantage	3.652	4	1.040
1	Natural attractions	3.580	4	1.145
11	Image of the destination	3.580	4	1.008
6	Availability of transportation to the destination	3.568	4	1.104
19	Respecting sustainable development of the destination	3.538	4	1.003
17	Uniqueness of destination	3.474	4	1.014
23	Involvement in action	3.335	3	0.995
2	Cultural attractions	3.278	3	1.153
18	Additional infrastructure	3.224	3	1.059
22	Winers in competitions	3.063	3	1.030
7	Local transportation	3.038	3	1.183
25	Sending newsletters	2.715	3	1.141

Following Table 2 shows the dependence of wine destinations quality factors on the gender and age of the respondents. The value “YES+” means that the dependency of the factor evaluation on age or gender was proven on the 5% significance level. The value “YES” represents the proven dependency on the 10% significance level only. The value “NO” explains that the dependency was not even proven on the 10% significance level.

Tab 2. Dependence of factors on gender and age. Source: authors research

Factor number	Quality Factor	Satisfaction		Importance	
		KW-test gender	KW-test age	KW-test gender	KW-test age
1	Natural attractions	NO	YES+	NO	YES+
2	Cultural attractions	YES+	NO	YES+	YES+
3	Accommodation	NO	NO	NO	YES+
4	Food	YES+	YES+	YES+	YES+
5	Social and experiential events	NO	NO	YES+	NO
6	Availability of transportation to the destination	NO	YES+	NO	YES+
7	Local transportation	NO	NO	NO	YES+
8	Availability and quality of information in the destination	NO	YES+	NO	YES+
9	Information and communication prior to arrival	NO	YES+	YES+	YES+
10	Friendly acceptance by the locals	NO	NO	YES+	YES+
11	Image of the destination	YES+	NO	NO	NO
12	Level of prices of services and goods in the destination	YES+	NO	NO	YES+
13	Level of personnel quality in tourism services	YES+	YES+	YES+	YES+
14	Sense of security	NO	YES+	NO	YES+
15	Destination cleanliness	NO	YES+	NO	YES+
16	Overcrowding of the destination	YES+	YES+	YES+	YES+
17	Uniqueness of destination	YES+	YES+	NO	NO
18	Additional infrastructure	YES+	YES+	NO	YES+
19	Respecting sustainable development of the destination	YES+	YES+	NO	NO
20	Quality of wine commentary	YES+	YES	YES+	YES+
21	Quality of wine	YES+	YES+	YES+	YES+
22	Winers in competitions	YES+	YES+	YES	YES+
23	Involvement in action	NO	NO	NO	YES+
24	Price advantage	X	X	NO	YES+
25	Sending of newsletters	X	X	NO	YES+

The dependence on gender at 5% significance level has been proven in case of 12 factors (52%) in satisfaction context and in case of 9 factors (36%) for importance evaluation. Age dependence has been demonstrated for over half of the factors both in researching the importance of factors and in assessing satisfaction as well (61%: 14 factors out of 23 for satisfaction; 81%: 21 factors out of 25 for importance). Six factors (4: Food, 13: The level of personnel quality in tourism services, 16: Overcrowding of the destination, 20: Quality of wine commentary, 21: Quality of wine, 22: Winners in competitions) are dependent on gender and age in both categories.

Tab 3. The performance of wine destination quality factors based on visitors' satisfaction (the order of quality factors based on customer satisfaction). Source: authors research (scale of satisfaction 1–5, where 5 – represented a very high satisfaction with the factor)

		Mean	Median	Std. Dev.
10	Friendly acceptance by the locals	4.622	5	0.707
21	Quality of wine	4.558	5	0.660
5	Social and experiential events	4.498	5	0.727
14	Sense of security	4.461	5	0.823
23	Involvement in action	4.404	5	0.752
15	Destination cleanliness	4.315	4	0.789
11	Image of the destination	4.262	4	0.858
20	Quality of wine commentary	4.258	4	0.861
1	Natural attractions	4.199	4	0.910
22	Winers in competitions	4.187	4	0.864
13	Level of personnel quality in tourism services	4.157	4	0.879
17	Uniqueness of destination	4.150	4	0.858
2	Cultural attractions	4.135	4	0.825
9	Information and communication prior to arrival	4.127	4	0.933
6	Availability of transportation to the destination	4.112	4	0.927
12	Level of prices of services and goods in the destination	4.112	4	0.833
16	Overcrowding of the destination	4.064	4	0.867
19	Respecting sustainable development of the destination	4.034	4	0.860
4	Food	3.974	4	0.838
3	Accommodation	3.970	4	0.845
8	Availability and quality of information in the destination	3.948	4	0.968
18	Additional infrastructure	3.764	4	0.922
7	Local transportation	3.734	4	0.974

The table 3 above describes the performance of the wine destination quality factors based on visitors' satisfaction. It is visible that visitors in the South Moravian region are the most satisfied with hospitality and friendly acceptance by the locals, with quality of wine and with the offer of various events taking place in this wine destination. On the opposite side of the scale are basically the infrastructural aspects of the destinations: local transport, other infrastructure, information security, accommodation.

Furthermore, we have linked the results of significance survey and satisfaction survey using the so-called IPA analysis (see Fig. 4), which allows us to better discover the practical implication of the obtained results.

Factors representing quadrant "keep up the good work" (F13: Level of personnel quality in tourism services, F20: Quality of wine commentary, F15: Destination cleanliness, 14: Sense of security, F5: Social and experiential events, F10: Friendly acceptance by the locals, 21: Quality of wine) were evaluated by clients as very positively and have high importance. Therefore, destination management and local businesses in South Moravia need to continue to deliver high-quality product. Factors (F4: Food, F3: Accommodation, F8: Availability and quality of information in the destination, F16: Overcrowding of the destination, F12: Level of prices of services and goods) with performance deficits "concentrate here" are characterized by high importance and low performance. These factors are important to a visitor, however, their present level of performance does not meet visitors' requirements. Therefore, heightened attention needs to be paid to these factors. Factors representing "low priority" quadrant (F7, F18, F19, F6, F9, F2) have low importance for visitors, thus having low impact on the performance of a destination. Companies

and local governments should not devote a lot of time to improve these as the return on investment could be minimal. Factors (F23, F11, F1, F22, F17) in last quadrant “possible overkill” are characterized by low importance and high performance, highlighting the fact that excessive importance is giving to the factor, yet, visitors “do not care.”

Fig 4. IPA analysis of wine destination: South Moravia. Source: authors’ research

5. Discussion: could the cultural tourism be an important driver of the rural development and under which conditions

For Czechia, which does not have any access to the sea neither high mountains, the cultural tourism is a big challenge. It shows that the country is competitively able in attractions for the cultural tourism but less prepared in the matters of the infrastructure, marketing, information and preparation of the human factor. As Fig. 8 shows, the most attractive and most frequently used tourist areas can be found especially in mountain areas of the borderland, whereas cultivated lowland areas of Moravia and Bohemia are considered far less attractive. The cultural tourism can modify such a general picture because cultural attractions are localised more equally.

Thousands of tangible and intangible attractions for the cultural tourism of different substance can be found in the Czech countryside. They cover the whole territory of the country with a high density. It enables to potentially disperse tourist on a wide territory and lighten to hard-pressed urban, UNESCO sites and resort areas. On the other hand, some of the constructions have dilapidated or are not in a good state.

Although the situation has improved since 1990s, the tourist infrastructure in rural Czechia lags behind traditional tourist countries. Rural population still mostly have the psychology of the productive workers. It is not fully prepared to serve for the tourists. Moreover, hardly any bigger investment capital can be found in the countryside. That is why the investors come from cities or even from abroad, which means that the connection between the attraction and the village is mediated only.

The accessibility of the Czech, especially peripheral countryside for tourists who prefer a combination of air/luxury bus is not very good. On the other hand, the Czech countryside is interconnected by the dense and frequent network of public transport and local roads. Consequently, the Czech countryside is accessible to slow tourists who have time to spend more

time in the area. In addition to this, high personal safety, low living costs, accessible first aid and medical care of a corresponding quality and general accessibility of the landscape, can be added.

Hospitality is considered a comparative advantage of the Czech rural areas. However, hospitality means that local people accept tourists they like. It would be necessary to complement the hospitality with the professionalism. It includes not only the knowledge of the technology of the tourist industry, but also a language knowledge (which is improving with the coming of new generation) and a professional approach to the guests. It was probably the main deficiency of people in tourist services in 1990s.

It is extremely important to offer individual rural regions as a package of tourist services including individual attractions of cultural, sport or relaxing tourism as one whole interconnected with appropriate accommodation, catering and other services. Individual providers have to learn that they are competitors and collaborators at the same time. In this field, LEADER action groups and commune association could play their role. The introduction of digital technologies is also extremely important (Bigné and Decrop, 2018).

Tourists willing to get a new knowledge about foreign regions, to perceive values of the rural landscape, rural constructions, rural gastronomy and habits of local people, are the right customers to which the Czech rural tourism should be directed. Such tourist would be probably also accepted by local people. Soft and slow tourism is desirable in relation to the cultural tourism. Additionally, cultural tourism could be less dependent on seasonal fluctuations (see e.g. Cisneros-Martínez and Fernandez-Marales (2015).

The international significance of attractiveness could be estimated according to the seats of the UNESCO cultural heritage. At the moment, there are 14 tangible items and 5 intangible ones on the World Heritage List and next 10 on the Tentative List. However, there are certainly additional motivations able to attract foreign cultural tourists. They are usually not so much connected with individual specific cultural monuments but they rather relate to the general interest of foreigners in Czech culture. The period of getting to know Czechia as a post-communist country are over. At the moment, the Czech countryside could offer rich cultural and natural heritage on a relatively small territory, a dense mosaic of easy accessible cultural values of different character and origin in a relative safe and not expensive milieu. The variability of the Czech cultural heritage could be compared to the biodiversity in the nature.

The tourism including the cultural one is rapidly developing branch of economy and a very important component of the transition to the post-productive society. It is one of the activities able to substitute the decrease of jobs in productive branches of economy. However, the tourism is hardly able to substitute the loss of rural jobs completely without risking the destruction of the attractiveness of the territory in the Czech conditions.

The tourism is especially important for rural areas where localisation of other economic branches is limited. In rural regions with minimum occasions for intensive mountain tourism, neither water tourism, the cultural tourism gains in importance. The cultural tourism could partly overcome the problem of seasonality – at least to widen the season from the spring to the late autumn.

The human factor seems to be decisive. The knowledge, skills, motivations and collaboration are the key factors creating the destination efforts. It is especially necessary to highlight the importance to offer not individual providers but the regions as a whole connecting different tourist activities. It is decisive to attract visitors for longer stays and thus for spending more money there.

In the first half of 2020, the entire tourism sector was hit by the corona-19 pandemic. Unlike other forms of tourism, cultural tourism has in many cases responded by introducing virtual tours. This made it possible to maintain its cognitive function, but did not bring any benefit to the regions. However, it can be assumed that tourists who have become acquainted with cultural attractions virtually may be motivated to visit them physically after the epidemy has subsided.

Consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic represent a new challenge for the development of the rural cultural tourism. Due to the risk or restriction of traveling abroad, the Czech population from foreign to domestic tourism brought new impulses for those segments of tourism that are

oriented mainly to domestic tourists. It is mainly rural tourism. The new normality after COVID-19 brought to the region countless opportunities and alliances between all tourist's Governmental and non-Governmental units. Suddenly, the segmentation of clients and seasonality in hotels has changed and the restart of economy had to be solved operatively. In South Moravia, a new extra-campaign #mimodavy (out of the crowds) was created, the aim of which is to direct tourists to less busy tourist areas. As a reaction to reanimate tourism after the pandemic, it was possible to further diversify visitors in the territory and thus make full use of the cultural and natural potential of regions. Great emphasis in traveling is placed on a personal approach.

The factor "Sense of security" was in the research on fourth place in the significance order. Its position can be expected to grow. Under this factor is hidden not only safety from the point of view of crime, but safety from the point of view of the health of tourists (low incidence of dangerous diseases, etc.). From the point of view of the Czechia and rural tourism, this can be considered as a real strength.

6. Conclusions

The overview of different activities shows that in the Czechia, there are a number of attractions of cultural tourism of various types, which are dislocated in the whole territory of the country. They are of international, national and regional importance. At the same time, however, it turns out that these attractions are concentrated mainly in cities. Accommodation and other infrastructure facilities show an even greater concentration in cities. This results in relatively higher revenues from urban tourism.

It follows from the case study that wine tourism is a young type of tourism in Czechia that has been evolving since the second half of the 1990s. Nowadays, wine tourism belongs to the most important segment of tourism in South Moravia. Undoubtedly, wine is an essential product of wine tourism, but visitor's satisfaction is influenced by many other factors especially soft intangible quality factors connected with human factor such as level of personnel quality in tourism services or friendly acceptance by the locals. During social events, it is necessary to manage over-tourism. Of course, we have to take into account the sense of security and destination cleanliness where security is considered as one of the strong competitive advantage of Czechia for domestic as well as foreign tourism market. Such factors are – to a certain extent – valid also for other forms of cultural tourism.

Various types of destinations are visited by different visitors with different motivation to travel, with specific desires and requirements for leisure, preferring a different season of travel, preferring different types of accommodation, boarding services or people with different budgets for their trip. The importance of knowing your visitor has a fundamental impact on destination management, strategy and destination product development, which can benefit not only destination management, but especially individual business entities in the destination. Czechia has a big potential for the cultural tourism development but its use asks for a great and lasting work of constantly reconciling the changing interests of tourists with the potential of the regions.

The process of the cultural rural tourism development should be a subject of further investigation. Relations between changing interests of tourists and the offer of providers will probably play the key role. It will happen under conditions of changing political, economic and environmental situation.

Acknowledgement

This paper is one of the results of the HORIZON 2020 project Social and innovative Platform On cultural Tourism and its potential towards deepening Europeanisation⁹, ID 870644, funding scheme Research and Innovation action, call H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-2019.

⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/870644>

- [1] Bambi, G., Iacobelli, S., Rossi, G., Pellegrini, P. & Barbari, M. (2019). Rural tourism to promote territories along the ancient roads of communication: case study of the rediscovery of the St. Francis's ways between Florence and La Verna. *European Countryside* 11(3), 462–474. DOI: 10.2478/euco-2019-0025.
- [2] Barbieri, C., Xu, S., Gil-Arroyo, C. & Rozier Rich, S. (2017). Agritourism, Farm Visit, or? A Branding Assessment for Recreation on Farms. *Journal of Travel Research* 55(8), 1094–1108. DOI: 10.1177/0047287515605930.
- [3] Blegoli, I., Hingley, M., del Chiappa, G. & Sodano, V. (2016). Challenges in Italian wine routes: managing stakeholders networks. *Quantitative Market Research* 19(2), 204–224. DOI: 10.1108/QMR-02-2016-0008.
- [4] Bigné, E. & Decrop, A. (2018). Paradoxes of postmodern tourists and innovation in tourism marketing. In Fayos-Solà E. & Cooper C., eds., *The Future of Tourism* (pp. 131–154). Springer, Cham. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-89941-1_7.
- [5] Bochenek, M. (2013). Festival tourism of folk group dancers from selected countries of the World. *Polish Journal of Sport Tourism* 20, 95–99. DOI: 10.2478/pjst-2013-0009.
- [6] Cisneros-Martínez, J. D., Fernandez-Morales, A. (2015). Cultural tourism as tourist segment for reducing seasonality in a coastal area: the case study of Andalusia. *Current Issues in Tourism* 18(8), 765–784. DOI: 10.1080/13683500.2013.861810.
- [7] Csapó, J. & Wetzl, V. (2016). Possibilities for the creation of beer routes in Hungary: a methodological and practical perspective. *European Countryside* 8(3), 250–262. DOI: 10.1515/euco-2016-0018.
- [8] Dunkley, R., Morgan, N. & Westwood, S. (2011). Visiting the trenches: exploring meanings and motivations in battlefield tourism. *Tourism Management* 32(4), 860–868. DOI: 10.1016/j.tourman.2010.07.011.
- [9] Dwyer, I., Kim, C. (2003). Destination competitiveness: Determinants and indicators. *Current Issues in Tourism*. 6(5), 369–414. DOI: 10.1080/13683500308667962.
- [10] Eusébio, C., Carneiro, M. J., Kastenholz, E., Figueiredo, E. & da Silva, D. S. (2017). Who is consuming the countryside? An activity-based segmentation analysis of the domestic rural tourism market in Portugal. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management* 31, 197–210. DOI: 10.1016/j.jhtm.2016.12.006.
- [11] Garau, C. (2015). Perspectives on Cultural and Sustainable Rural Tourism in a Smart Region: The Case Study of Marmilla in Sardinia (Italy). *Sustainability* 7(6), 6412–6434. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su7066412>.
- [12] Gheorghe, G., Tudorache, P. & Nistoreanu, P. (2014). Gastronomic tourism, a new trend for contemporary tourism? *Cactus Tourism Journal* 9(1), 12–21.
- [13] Gómez y Patiño, M., Xavier Medina, F. & Puyelo Arilla, J. M. (2016). New trends in tourism? From globalization to postmodernism. *International Journal of Scientific Management Tourism* 2(3), 417–433.
- [14] Granberg, L. (2017). From Agriculture to Tourism: Constructing New Relations Between Rural Nature and Culture in Lithuania and Finland. In Alanen, I., ed., *Mapping the Rural Problem in the Baltic Countryside* (20 p.). London: Routledge. DOI: 10.4324/9781351153287.
- [15] Griffin, K.A. & Raj, R. (2017): The importance of religious tourism and pilgrimage: reflecting on definitions, motives and data. *International Journal of Religious Tourism and Pilgrimage* 5(3), Article 2.
- [16] Hall, D. (2017). *Tourism and Geopolitics*. Wallingford: CABI.

- [17] Hall, D. & Mitchel, M. (2011). Rural tourism business as sustained and sustainable development? In Hall, D., Kirkpatrick, I. & Mitchell, M., eds., *Rural Tourism and Sustainable Business* (pp. 353–363). Clevedon: Channel View Publications.
- [18] Härfst, J., Pizzera, J. & Simic, S. (2015). Industrial heritage, cultural resources of current industries and creative pioneers – utilizing Industrial Culture in Central Europe. *Revija za geografijo* 11(2), 47–56.
- [19] Hassan, S. (2000). Determinants of market competitiveness in an environmentally sustainable tourism industry. *Journal of Travel Research*, 38(3), 239–245. DOI: 10.1177/004728750003800305.
- [20] Hughes, H. & Allen, D. (2005). Cultural tourism in Central and eastern Europe: the views of “induced image formation agents”. *Tourism Management* 26(2), 173–183. DOI: 10.1016/j.tourman.2003.08.021.
- [21] Kumar Dixit, S., ed. (2019). *The Routledge Handbook of Gastronomic Tourism*. Milton Park: Routledge.
- [22] Lane, B. (1994). What is rural tourism? *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* 2(1–2), 7–21. DOI: 10.1080/09669589409510680.
- [23] Lane B., Kastenholz, E. (2015). Rural tourism: the evolution of practice and research approaches—towards a new generation concept? *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* 23(8–9), 1133–1156. DOI: 10.1080/09669582.2015.1083997.
- [24] McIntosh, R. W., Goeldner, C. R. & Ritchie, J. R. B. (1995). *Tourism: principles, practices, philosophies*. 7th ed. New York: John Wiley and Sons.
- [25] Mousavi, S. S., Doratli, N., Mousavi, S. N. & Moradiahari, F. (2016). Defining cultural tourism. In Davic, P. & El-Haway, M., eds., *International Conference on Civil Architecture and Sustainable Development*. International Institute of Chemical, Biological and Environmental Engineering. DOI: 10.15242/IICBE.DIR1216411.
- [26] Pásková, M. (2009). *Udržitelnost rozvoje cestovního ruchu*. Hradec Králové: Gaudeamus.
- [27] Peruthová, A., Ryglová, K. (2018). Genderové rozdíly ve vnímání kvality venkovské destinace cestovního ruchu. *Acta Academica Karviniensia* 18(1), 59–67. DOI: 10.25142/aak.2018.006.
- [28] Poria, Y., Reichel, A. & Cohen, R. (2013). Tourist perspectives of World Heritage Site and its designation. *Tourism Management* 35, 272–274. DOI: 10.1016/j.tourman.2012.02.011.
- [29] Prokeš, M. (2019). Wine trails in the Czech Republic. In Sigala, M., Robinson, R., eds., *Wine tourism destination management and marketing: theory and cases* (pp. 341–355). Cham: Palgrave Macmillan. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-00437-8.
- [30] Rašovská, I., Kubíčková, M., Ryglová, K. (2020). Importance–performance analysis approach to destination management. *Tourism Economics*. DOI: 10.1177/1354816620903913.
- [31] Reijnders, S. (2016). *Places of the Imagination. Media, Tourism, Culture*. London: Routledge.
- [32] Richards, G. & Bonink, C. (1995). Marketing cultural tourism in Europe. *Journal of Vacation Marketing* 1(2), 172–180. DOI: 10.1177/135676679500100205.
- [33] Richards, G. (1996). *Cultural tourism in Europe*. Wallingford: CAB International.
- [34] Richards, G. (2018). Cultural tourism: a review of recent research and trends. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management* 36, 12–21. DOI: 10.1016/j.jhtm.2018.03.005.
- [35] Roca, Z. (2016). *Second Home Tourism in Europe: Lifestyle Issues and Policy Responses*. Abingdon: Routledge.
- [36] Ryglová, K., Rašovská, I. & Šácha, J. (2017). Rural Tourism – Evaluating the Quality of Destination. *European Countryside* 9(4), 769–778. DOI: 10.1515/euco-2017-0043.

- [37] Ryglová, K., Rašovská, I., Šácha, J. & Maráková, V. (2018). Building Customer Loyalty in Rural Destinations as a Pre-Condition of Sustainable Competitiveness. *Sustainability* 10(4), 957. DOI: 10.3390/su10040957.
- [38] Sever, I. (2015). Importance-performance analysis: A valid management tool? *Tourism Management* 48, 43–53. DOI: 10.1016/j.tourman.2014.10.022.
- [39] Silva, L. & Leal, J. (2015). Rural tourism and national identity building in contemporary Europe: Evidence from Portugal. *Journal of Rural Studies* 38, 109–119. DOI: 10.1016/j.jrurstud.2015.02.005.
- [40] Šťastná, M., Vaishar, A. & Pákozdiová, M (2015). Role of tourism in the development of peripheral countryside. Case studies of Eastern Moravia and Romanian Banat. *Forum Geographic* 14(1), 83–93. DOI: 10.5775/fg.2067-4635.2015.198.i.
- [41] Šťastná, M., Vaishar, A., Vavrouchová, H., Ševelová, M., Doskočilová, V., Lincová, H., Stonawská, K., Thonnová, P. & Vasyľchenko, A. (2015). *Cestovní ruch jako alternativní odvětví pro rozvoj jihomoravského venkova?* Brno: Mendel University in Brno.
- [42] Stoffelen, A. & Vanneste, D. (2015). Institutional (dis)integration and regional development implications of whisky tourism in Speyside, Scotland. *Scandinavian Journal of Hospitality and Tourism* 16(1), 42–60. DOI: 10.1080/15022250.2015.1062416.
- [43] Storey, D. (2004). A sense of place: rural development, tourism and place promotion in the Republic of Ireland. In Holloway, L. & Kneafsey, M., eds., *Geographies of rural cultures and societies* (pp. 197–213). Aldershot: Ashgate.
- [44] Strzelecka, M., Bynum Boley, B. & Strzelecka, C. (2016). Empowerment and resident support for tourism in rural Central and Eastern Europe (CEE): the case of Pomerania, Poland. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* 25(4), 554–572. DOI: 10.1080/09669582.2016.1224891.
- [45] Szörényiné Kukorelli, I. (2011). Tourism and agriculture in Hungary: post-productivist transition or new function in rural space? In Torres, R. M. & Henshall Momsen, J., eds., *Tourism and agriculture* (pp. 1327). London: Routledge.
- [46] Vasiliadis, L., Trivellas, P., Belias, D., Meleas, J., Kyriakou, D. & Koustelios, A. (2015). Cultural tourism revisited: the case of Thessaly. In Katsoni, V. & Stratigea, A., eds., *Tourism and Culture in the Age of Innovation* (pp. 69–78). Cham: Springer.
- [47] Vystoupil, J., ed. (2006). *Atlas cestovního ruchu České republiky*. Praha: Ministry of Regional Development.
- [48] Vystoupil, J. & Šauer, M. (2006). *Základy cestovního ruchu*. Brno: Masaryk university.
- [49] Wallace, G. & Russell, A. (2004). Eco-cultural tourism as a means for the sustainable development of culturally marginal and environmentally sensitive regions. *Tourist Studies* 4(3), 235–254. DOI: 10.1177/1468797604057326.
- [50] Woods, M. (2011). *Rural*. Abingdon: Routledge.
- [51] Zelenka, J. & Pásková, M. (2012). *Výkladový slovník cestovního ruchu*. 2nd ed. Praha. Linde.

Other sources

- [52] *Number of visitors to tourist destinations in 2018* (2019). Praha: Czech Tourism Agency.